
Research

Grassroots Training and Capacity Building as Essential Components of a Framework for Enhancing Equality in Mali's Educational Sector

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Abstract: This study examined the relevance of grassroots training and capacity building as essential components of a framework for enhancing equality in Mali's educational sector. This study adopted the human rights-based approach to development. A qualitative research approach was applied in carrying out this research. The population was made up of institutions involved in gender and educational issues in Mali. There was the use of quota, purposive (expert-based), and snowballing (chain) sampling techniques. The study used quota and purposive sampling techniques, with data collected using in-depth interviews and documentary analysis. The data were analyzed thematically, with the findings presented in line with the research questions. The study noted that education is a basic human right and that access to it is vital to sustainable development, as well as training and capacity building, especially for males at grassroots levels. It was pointed out that a number of factors compromise the utility of grassroots training in gender-related issues, including traditional cultural practices. The exclusion of women from active leadership roles and the crisis of females domestically, especially at grassroots levels, were seen as other cultural barriers. This study also pointed out that girls and women face a double burden, that is, the need to balance household and school responsibilities. The study found that numerous initiatives have been set up both at the continental and international levels to support girls and women around the world in achieving gender equality and empowering women. The research recommended that the Malian government ought to enforce human rights and take measures to outlaw traditional and cultural practices, which violate the rights of girls and women. There is a need for effective policies aimed at supporting care and domestic work which can be summarized by the 'quadruple R framework', which aims to recognize, reduce, and redistribute care and domestic work, as well as to represent carers in policymaking. The framework for grassroots training and capacity building of women and girls calls for action from the national, community, family, and individual levels. At each level, it is essential to ensure multiple interactions with multiple stakeholders.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Education, Empowerment, Gender Equality, Grassroots Training, National Gender Machinery

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Introduction

Despite the presence of a cocktail of legal and institutional frameworks on gender equality that apply in most countries of the world, men's and women's conditions of participation in the economy remain woefully unequal (Okeke-Uzodike 2019). In Africa, inequalities between women and men are among the greatest in the world, and this could be blamed on cultural practices, that hinder access to education by the girl child. Women and girls constitute about 52% of the population in Mali, which is more than half of the population, and yet they face a myriad of disadvantages. The United Nations (2022) notes that gender inequality persists worldwide, depriving women and girls of their basic rights and opportunities. Achieving gender equality and the empowerment of women and girls will require vigorous efforts, including legal frameworks to address deeply rooted gender-based discrimination often resulting from patriarchal attitudes and related social norms (United Nations, 2022).

It is also essential to note that the rights of children are a global concern and their well-being is one of the core issues that dominate policymaking debates. Vandergrift (2019) points out that, in most countries, there are debates pertaining to the rights of children, religious practices, and cultural diversity. According to Vandergrift (2019), the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), seeks to ensure that the rights of children are not compromised by religious and cultural practices. Pillay (2022) agrees with Vandergrift (2019) and states some religious and cultural practices threaten the realization of the 'best interests of the child' (BIC) involving children that include sexual and psychological abuse of children, contravening Articles 19, 34, and 36 of the CRC (United Nations, 2019).

Despite the existence of religious and cultural practices that compromise the rights of children, it is paramount to take care of the children, as espoused in the 1924 Declaration on the Rights of the Child (Phillips, 2021). According to Mporfu and Chimhenga (2016), it is essential that all decisions and interventions relating to children must be in their best interests. Pillay (2022) states that the BIC covers a number of issues, that include the right to stay in a proper home, the right not to be separated from parents and siblings, and the right to education.

Green (2014) argues that education is essential in one's life and it enhances chances for a higher standard of living. The CRC provides that, "state parties ought to recognize the right of the child to education and with a view to achieving this right progressively and based on equal opportunity (United Nations Children's Fund, UNICEF, 2017). According to Article 28 of the CRC, there must be equal opportunity and access to education for all children. Additionally, Human Rights Watch (2022) quotes the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which states that everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit.

According to the United Nations Education, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2016), the legal framework on the rights of children includes the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (ACRWC), the Copenhagen Declaration on Social Development, the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action, and the Dakar Framework for Action. In addition to the laws, there is a myriad of institutional frameworks for ensuring the attainment of the rights of children. Internationally, UNICEF is particularly interested in the rights and welfare of children. There are other United Nations organs, for instance, UNESCO, which focuses on the provision of education. In Mali, various

government ministries and departments aim to ensure the attainment of children's rights. For instance, the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education is concerned about access to education.

In light of the elaborate legal and institutional framework pertaining to the right to education by every child, the question is, to what extent is this right being realized by the girl child in Mali? It seems as if the provisions of the UDHR and Article 28 of the CRC are not being attained because there is consensus among many scholars that the girl child lacks access to education (Agbaje et al., 2015; Banda and Atansah, 2016; and Brixiova and Kangoye, 2019). Vandemoortele (2020) opines: children, the world over, seem not to have access to adequate educational facilities. The assertion by Vandemoortele (2020) agrees with an earlier statement by Save the Children Sweden (2015) that family setup and poverty were among the factors responsible for the lack of access to education.

In Mali, education is compulsory from ages six to 15. However, many children do not attend school, and girls' enrolment is lower than that of boys at all levels due to factors such as poverty, societal preference to educate boys, child marriage and sexual harassment. Women's literacy rate (aged 15 and over) is significantly lower than that of men: female 22.2%, compared to male 45.1% (Government of Mali, 2021). In this regard, this study examined the relevance of grassroots training and capacity building as essential components of a framework for enhancing equality in the Malian educational sector. The specific research objectives were to:

1. Examine the significance of grassroots training and capacity building on enhancing access to education by the girl child in Mali;
2. Interrogate the factors compromising the utility of grassroots training and capacity building in gender-related issues; and
3. Propose a framework for enhancing the utility of grassroots training and capacity-building interventions in the Malian educational sector.

Theoretical Framework: Human Rights-Based Approach to Development

This study adopted the human rights-based approach to development. Education is a basic human right and access to it is vital for sustainable development. In addition, UNICEF (2017) stated that seven principles guide the rights-based approach to development. These are:

- i. **Universal and inalienability:** All the people in the world are entitled to them;
- ii. **Indivisibility:** Every person has an equal right to them;
- iii. **Interdependence and interrelatedness:** The realization of one right has a connection with the other rights;
- iv. **Equality and non-discrimination:** All individuals are equal as human beings;
- v. **Participation and inclusion:** Every person has the entitlement to participate and enjoy the rights;
- vi. **Empowerment:** The capabilities of the people to demand and realize their rights ought to grow; and
- vii. **Accountability and respect for the rule of law:** Focus is on the need to ensure that the government institutions are answerable to the people in relation to the enjoyment of their rights. There must be equality in the enjoyment of rights (Human Rights Watch, 2022).

The rights-based approach is applicable in this study because of the fact that all children must enjoy their rights. No child must be excluded from realizing the right to education.

Research Methodology

The study applied qualitative research on gender, and development as complex issues that cannot be fully appreciated without detailed analysis. The population was made up of institutions involved in gender and educational issues in Mali. There was the use of quota, purposive (expert-based), and snowballing (chain) sampling techniques. Data were collected using in-depth interviews and documentary analysis. The data were analyzed thematically, with the findings presented in line with the research questions.

Findings

The findings of the study are presented in line with the three research objectives. The first research objective was to examine the significance of grassroots training and capacity building in enhancing access to education by the girl child in Mali. The second objective sought to interrogate the factors compromising the utility of grassroots training and capacity building in gender-related issues. The third objective was to propose a framework for enhancing the utility of grassroots training and capacity-building interventions in the Malian educational sector.

Significance of Grassroots Training and Capacity Building on Enhancing Access to Education by the Girl Child in Mali

Training and capacity building, especially of males at grassroots levels is paramount. There is growing interest in the question of men's roles in fostering gender equality. The perception that it is desirable to involve men in efforts toward gender equality is rapidly becoming institutionalized in the methods and programs of international organizations. Local programmes that engage men have proliferated in fields such as sexual and reproductive health, violence prevention, parenting, and education. At the same time, policies and programmes addressing men in gender-conscious ways are scattered and underdeveloped.

One of the reasons why so many programmes missed the mark is that too many gender initiatives focus solely on changing women, from the way they network to the way they lead. For a long time, a commitment to promoting gender equality in economic outcomes, as in other areas of social development and human rights, has emphasized women's empowerment. Yet, training and capacity building of men is also necessary though for a more direct reason. According to Ramparsad (2019), male involvement and participation are significant and critical in advancing gender equality as men play a key role in influencing the corrosive patriarchal attitudes and norms in society. To achieve gender equality, many men's attitudes and behaviours must change. Men often play a crucial role as 'gatekeepers' of the current gender order through their responsibilities as decision-makers and leaders within their families and communities. They may participate in sexist practices and maintain unjust gender relations by perpetrating violence against women, controlling women's reproductive and familial decision-making, limiting women's access to community resources and political power, or espousing patriarchal beliefs and norms that allow other men to engage in such actions (Roux et al., 2017).

Moreover, there is also a need to build the capacity of women to engage in business activities so that society can view them as equal to men, and in turn place value on girl child education. For instance, to mitigate the challenges of gender inequality, Peru implemented entrepreneurial training programmes that were aimed at developing women's creative industries by supporting networks of women and indigenous communities and by providing training on better manufacturing techniques and marketing (Ferdousi and Mahmud, 2019). By setting up workshops for women in the four regions, the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO, 2017) helped to improve social inclusion and equality of opportunity. Overall, providing support to traditional creative industries, which are a priority for Peru, has had tangible effects on women's empowerment by putting decision-making in women's hands and giving them the skills, they need to grow their businesses. Moreover, Brixiova and Kangoye (2019) point out that there was a

lack of appreciation of women's creative ability and there was implementation of the Women Entrepreneurship Development Programme. Accordingly, the UNIDO programme promoted women entrepreneurs in various business ventures, in the process creating over 650 women trainers who passed on valuable knowledge to as many as 16,000 women (UNIDO, 2017).

Factors Compromising Utility of Grassroots Training and Capacity Building in Gender-Related Issues

According to Ademiluka (2018), traditional cultural practices tend to reflect the values, beliefs, and ways of doing things that are held by the members of a community. Every societal grouping has basic values that it respects and it is not easy to change the practices. Despite the fact that their harmful nature and their violation of international human rights laws, such practices persist because they are not questioned and take on an aura of morality in the eyes of those practising them. Accordingly, grassroots training and capacity-building activities may be compromised by resistance. In addition, the exclusion of women from active leadership roles and the crisis of females domestically especially at grassroots levels were seen as less influential cultural barriers in this regard. One of the interviewees said that there is exclusion of rural women in active leadership roles, thus, when it comes to educational rights, girls tend to be overlooked. Due to patriarchy, girls and women, and the work that they do tend to be devalued and discouraged. Thus, sociocultural challenges can be viewed as the negative attitude that society has towards women engaging in business. Women have been excluded from active roles in major institutions such as churches, and local entities. Traditional and cultural expectations define the role of girls and women in society and in the family. In both rural, traditional communities and urban areas, deep-rooted social norms continue to dictate which types of jobs are 'acceptable' for women, and these norms also place a heavier share of domestic responsibilities on women.

This study also found that there is a crisis of female domesticity, especially at grassroots levels. Firstly, there is the issue of 'stable marriages', which gives women a long-time horizon in forming their expectations about the support that will be provided by their husbands and a sense of security in these relations. There is male domination that encourages the economic dependency of women on men and reinforces the sense of the motherly role as natural. There are also limited work opportunities and, for women in rural areas, domesticity becomes a more attractive practical alternative than when there are lots of interesting and well-paid work opportunities available. In addition, there is the principle of the 'family wage', in which the earnings of the male breadwinner should be sufficient to support a family. Finally, there are cultural and social supports for the domesticity of women.

Related to cultural practices, there is also the problem of gender-based violence (GBV). Almost all the interview and focus group discussion participants acknowledged the increase in cases of gender-based violence, which negatively compromises entrepreneurial activity by both men and women. GBV is one of the most common yet unacknowledged and serious human rights violations, not just in Mali, but in the whole world. The prevalence of all forms of violence against women, especially physical and sexual violence, compromises efforts towards girl child education and women empowerment.

It is also essential to note that women who are abused in their homes by their partners tend to exhibit spiritual emptiness, emotional trauma, social isolation, financial problems and physical injuries as a result of the abuse they suffer at the hands of their significant others, thereby compromising their ability to engage in viable business ventures. Literature supports these findings and Ncube (2018) argues that abuse is perpetuated by the women's lack of knowledge, failure to speak out about the abuse, cultural practices, insecurities and commitment to the relationship, and sometimes in the hope that the perpetrators will change. In some cases, money becomes the cause of tension, where women can be denied access to economic resources by their partners, or have to submit their salaries to their husbands who take complete control of such monies.

Almost all the participants in this study argued that women are objects of patriarchal discourse and narratives. It was held that women are portrayed in stereotyped images that emphasize passive, submissive qualities and this influences them to play a subordinate role in society. Most participants argued that women are viewed as sex and reproductive objects. More so, it is believed that women focus much on their domestic roles thereby reducing their zeal to self-actualization.

This study also pointed out that girls face a double burden, that is, the need to balance household and school responsibilities. Almost all the women who took part in this research said that it is not easy to manage this double burden. One of the interviewees said: "Double female burden of being a family person responsible for unpaid housework, upbringing of children and that of being an entrepreneur is a drawback to many females starting or running their own businesses." The unpaid care and domestic work disproportionately carried out by women is a critical barrier to women's economic empowerment, as it limits their ability to venture into business.

This study also found that there is a lack of confidence and self-esteem, especially among rural girls and women. An official in the Ministry of Women's Affairs had this to say: "A major problem relates to women's confidence, in both the beliefs in their own abilities, as well as in the capability of communicating confidence". In general, men can be characterized as more confident than women, especially regarding financial decisions. Women's lower confidence, especially regarding financial matters, is also reflected in the fact that businesswomen generally report lower levels of profitability. Women are often stereotyped as being more apologetic. One interesting study found that women do indeed apologize more but only because women judge themselves more harshly, and not because they are more willing to apologize.

Another interviewee pointed out that gender behavioral traits are a key issue, whereby women tend to undervalue their own skills, achievements and experiences. All these factors have negative implications for girl child education. In addition, the relatively low number of successful female role models often compounds stereotypes and reinforces perceived difficulties in rising up the corporate ladder. Even if it is feasible for women to aspire to leadership positions, they will not know this, or be motivated to try, unless they see other women filling similar positions, or are otherwise informed that these positions are open to them. Almost all the interviewees argued that there is also the challenge of aversion to competition. Women's preference for non-competitive environments may limit their drive to contest in an electoral race or competitive corporate advancement process.

Enhancing Utility of Grassroots Training and Capacity Building Interventions

This study pointed out that numerous initiatives have been set up both at continental and international levels to support women around the world with the goal of achieving gender equality and empowering women at all levels. The United Nations' SDG Number 5 seeks to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. Goal 5 recognizes the critical role women play in society and the challenges they come across which include but are not limited to violence and unfair labour practices, and therefore advocates for the advancement of women in various areas such as politics and the economy, and the ending of violence against women (United Nations, 2022). On the other hand, the African Union through its African Women's Decade initiatives aims to accelerate the status of women in various fields such as education, agriculture and governance. Thus, the year 2015 was also declared the year of Women Empowerment and Development toward Africa's Agenda 2063 by the African Union (African Union, 2015).

According to Glover et al. (2018), governments ought to enforce human rights and take strong measures to outlaw traditional and cultural practices which violate the rights of women. For instance, the move by many countries, including Mali to criminalize child marriages is noble. With such policies, it may be easy for grassroots training and capacity-building initiatives to be implemented. Existing policies and legislative instruments that are in place should be reinforced. There is a need to address the existence of the experience of a dual legal system in most countries, especially in Africa. Unyielding cultural attitudes that flow from a patriarchal society which do not place equal value and worth on

women's rights should be addressed (Roux et al., 2017). In South Africa, for example, Ramparsad (2019), argues that the Constitution makes the achievement of equality a foundational value of the nation. Section 9 of the Constitution of South Africa guarantees the right to equality and does so by providing for equality of all before the law, allowing for positive redress measures to advance previously disadvantaged persons, and prohibiting unfair discrimination by the state and by individuals (Ncube, 2018). In addition, the South African Constitution includes provisions that consider the need for the state to actively advance equitable access to national resources. The National Policy Framework for Women Empowerment and Gender Equality is a key policy which is meant to enable the mainstreaming of gender as a strategy for gender equality. Emanating from this policy is the establishment of the National Gender Machinery (NGM) within the South African State (Ramparsad, 2019). There is a need for the acceleration of socio-economic transformation and implementation for women's empowerment and participation through oversight, monitoring, evaluation and influencing policy (Ramparsad, 2019). Through their social, political and economic participation and empowerment efforts, the National Gender Machinery ought to create opportunities that exist within the social, justice and governance sub-sectors and also promote and protect the rights of women in related areas. This, they hope will aid in promoting women's full participation in decision-making so that their social and basic needs move from the margins to the center of development, planning and resource allocation. In Mali, the government made changes through policy implementation and law amendments to try and reduce gender inequality by ratifying international conventions and protocols. These treaties and protocols aim to address gender inequality and include the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), and the African Charter on Human and People's Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol). The Constitution of Mali has provisions against discrimination, which include customary values and practices (African Development Bank, 2014). The Government of Mali has also enacted several statutes and regulations aimed at protecting women from gender-based violence. These include the Domestic Violence Act and the National Gender Policy.

Moreover, Okeke-Uzodike (2019) argue that there is a need for effective policies aimed at supporting care and domestic work which can be summarized in the 'quadruple R framework', which aims to recognize, reduce and redistribute care and domestic work, as well as the representation of carers in policymaking. This involves responses across public and private care services and the labour market, including improved maternity, paternity and parental leave and breastfeeding policies, and improved legal protection and working conditions for care and domestic workers. Key policy challenges involve the expansion of benefits to the informal economy, and ensuring that government programmes, such as social protection and early childhood care and education initiatives, are gender-responsive and aimed at the alleviation of women's unpaid care loads (Longman and Bradley, 2015).

The International Labour Organization (2019) argues that social protection can help alleviate gender gaps in poverty rates, reduce vulnerability to economic shocks, and support women to overcome barriers to business and labour market participation, including through the redistribution of unpaid care loads onto public care services. The social protection instruments, which support women's economic empowerment may emphasize legal protection for maternity, paternity and parental leave, unemployment benefits, childcare support, employment guarantee schemes, including public works programmes, and social pension and micro-pension schemes (Pillay, 2022). Developing a robust strategy to ensure adequate fiscal space to scale up social protection and services is critical to the achievement of women's economic empowerment. Although this remains highly challenging in a global context of fiscal contraction and structural adjustment, a number of countries have taken steps to scale up enabling initiatives. For example, Mexico's Estancias childcare programme has received continued funding to ensure its growth, providing increased childcare facilities to support women's entry into business ventures, and the labor market (Phillips, 2021).

According to Samkange (2015), women's voice and leadership in decision-making are closely associated with economic empowerment. Rural women's ability to take on leadership positions, organize with others and have a voice in decision-making is critical to ensure that the diverse needs and preferences of women are made central to efforts to

further women's economic empowerment, including economic decision-making. Vandergrift (2019) quotes the arguments from the 1995 United Nations Fourth World Conference on Women, which pointed out that absolute poverty and the feminization of poverty, unemployment, the increasing fragility of the environment, continued violence against women and the widespread exclusion of half of humanity from institutions of power and governance underscore the need to continue the search for development, peace and security and for ways of assuring people-centered sustainable development. The participation and leadership of the half of humanity that is female is essential to the success of that search and has positive implications for girl child education.

Vandemoortele (2020) points out that leadership and collective action take myriad forms, and are strongly associated with improved productivity and working conditions, as well as changes to workers' rights and protections and women's increased skills, confidence and self-belief, as well as wider changes in restrictive social norms. Collectives may include workers' unions, cooperatives or women's rights organizations. In turn, women's economic participation can strengthen women's voice, leadership and collective bargaining power. However, the extent to which economic participation is empowering and transformative in women's lives depends on a range of factors, including the type and quality of work, the extent to which economic participation is coupled with additional opportunities to strengthen women's capabilities and shift constricting social norms, the social acceptability of their work, and women's experiences of class/caste and socio-cultural discrimination. The provision of flexible and sustainable funding to women's collectives is an important means of supporting women's increased voice, leadership and economic decision-making. Equally critical is ensuring that their participation is meaningful and that the institutions they operate within both recognize their legitimacy and are responsive to their demands. For example, without responsive, democratic governance, in both public and private institutions, the effectiveness of women's advocacy will remain limited.

Moreover, according to Tolander (2013), the human rights-based approach to development aims to overcome the deficits of other approaches, by addressing structures that may cause underdevelopment, such as inequality in power. A rights-based approach treats development issues as matters of obligation and right, rather than discretion or charity. Green (2014: 13) argues, "The human rights framework is precise as it sets out clearly who has obligations and duties and who has not, and what those obligations and duties are." The human rights-based approach is practical as it provides states with a formal language they can use to negotiate and cooperate with one another. The approach is also binding, and "when governments ratify human rights agreements, they accept a formal duty to implement the commitments they have thereby made" (Tolander, 2013: 21). On a deeper level, "there is a need for an understanding that they have rights can be a life-changing 'light-bulb moment' in people's lives. A rights-based approach also encourages personal agency, recognizes poor people as full citizens at the core of progressive change, and not having to be regarded as the 'beneficiaries' waiting helplessly for the others to come to their rescue" (Green, 2014: 13).

Moreover, "a rights framework can serve a similar function for activists and aid workers, acting as a compass to help them steer through the messiness of reality" (Serrat, 2017: 21). When implementing the human rights-based approach, a number of questions are raised, for example, "What are the rights involved in this situation? Whose rights are being violated? Will the intervention strengthen their exercise?" (Green, 2014: 13). Accordingly, "the approach keeps focusing on the most marginalized people. It thus forces us to continually think how work can reach those who otherwise would lose out on its benefits". The human rights-based approach "also puts emphasis on actors; it provides clarity on who has to deliver what in the 'social contract' (though admittedly lines can get blurry) and pushes you to analyze what holds them back from fulfilling their responsibilities" (Serrat, 2017: 21). The right-based framework also provides a clear and accepted basis for discussion and a leverage point for debates on improvements. There is no 'would be nice to have' rights as they are legally protected entitlements.

Framework for Enhancing Utility of Grassroots Training and Capacity Building Interventions in the Malian Educational Sector

The government of Mali and its development partners have been making concerted efforts towards women's empowerment in rural areas. However, the absence of entrepreneurial skills is compromising the success of the programmes as women sometimes lack adequate knowledge for effectively managing the projects' financial resources. Accordingly, in this study, entrepreneurial training was seen as a catalyst, which could enhance the success of policies and programmes directed towards empowering rural women. The success of the training programmes requires the interaction of multiple stakeholders, who would operate at the national, regional, district, ward and village levels. Grassroots training and capacity building are essential for girl child educational rights and women's empowerment, but there is also a need for an enabling macro-environment, cultural changes, and a positive mindset on the part of the women. The framework for enhancing the success of girl child and empowerment in Mali is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1: Framework for Enhancing Grassroots Training Capacity Building

Formulated by Researchers (2023)

The Framework in Fig. 1 shows that there is a need for action from the national, community, family, and individual levels. At each level, it is essential to ensure multiple interactions with multiple stakeholders. In addition, behavioral change is necessary at the national, community, family and individual levels. At the individual level girls and women ought to invest in their education and training. Behavior change and personal investment are important for the development of high-potential female entrepreneurs. Moreover, success in the area of women's empowerment depends on effective implementation.

Conclusion

Education is a conscious process of knowledge acquisition and skills development for the purpose of developing a 'knowledge society', and is essential for every human being. The challenge of delivering sustainable economic growth that benefits all human beings can be managed if there is the use of all available resources, including women. Leaving the girl child and women behind means foregoing the important contributions women make to the economy. In this regard, quality education is part of the global development agenda and Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Number 4 stresses emphasis on ensuring that there is an inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. In addition, SDG Goal 8 emphasizes the promotion of sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all. There is also SDG Goal 9 that advocates for the promotion of inclusive and sustainable industrialization and fosters innovation by every member of the society in Mali.

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